

Diamond Light Source Experimental Report

MM21716: Quadrupolar X-ray Magnetic Circular Dichroism using Superchiral X-rays

Principal Investigator
Experiment Team

Prof Steve Collins, Diamond Light Source
Dr Joel Collins, University of Bath
Prof Stephen Lovesey, Diamond Light Source

Local contact

Prof Steve Collins, Diamond Light Source

Date of Experiment Sun 15 Sep 2019

Instruments I16

1. Abstract

Our experiment aimed to demonstrate an enhancement of electric quadrupole – electric quadrupole (E2-E2) contributions to x-ray magnetic circular dichroism (XMCD) in a crystals of holmium iron garnet by the use of ‘superchiral’ x-rays [1]. To this end, we generated a superchiral standing field within a very high quality crystal by aligning to a Bragg reflection, close to backscattering, with circularly polarized x-rays. XMCD, as measured by the fluorescence signal, is then expected to be enhanced for quadrupole transitions. (In fact, the large reduction in electric dipole events, even more than the modest increase in quadrupole signal, should yield a significant effective quadrupole enhancement). The experiment is essentially carried out by observing a change in XMCD with the precise Bragg angle, in the close vicinity of the reflection.

Holmium iron garnet is that it exhibits a zero magnetization ‘compensation point’ at $T \sim 140$ K, where the holmium moments are exactly cancelled by the net moment of the antiferromagnetically-coupled tetragonal and octahedral iron sub-lattice, expecting to cause a reversal of the XMCD signal with temperature.

2. Experiment details

The current experiment hinges on finding a sample material with a strong standing-wave intensity for a Bragg reflection close to backscattering, with a photon energy that matches an absorption edge exhibiting strong XMCD. The best match we have found so far is the (0016) Bragg reflection in holmium iron garnet (HoIG), at the Ho L3 edge (8.071 keV). The sample – a very high quality single crystal of a few mm in dimensions – was grown at the University of Oxford [2]. It exhibited several high-quality cleavage planes but as {001} is not a natural cleavage plane of these garnets, a face was cut with a laser cutter. The process left some surface damage that was removed by mechanical polishing and acid etching.

The experimental setup required either the Si (111) or (333) monochromator reflection set close to the Ho L3 edge energy, circularly polarized x-ray, near backscattering geometry, and a magnetic field to ‘flip’ the polarization of HoIG. The sample, Figure 1, was cooled with a helium gas-jet cooler, down to around 20 K, with the sample and magnet contained within a helium bag to remove air from the cold sample, cf. Figure 2. XMCD was measured in fluorescence mode using the beamline’s Pilatus 100K x-ray area detector. Circular polarization was generated by the I16 diamond quarter-wave phase-retarder.

Figure 1: The HoIG crystal sample, mounted on a stiff insulating ceramic holder, prior to installing the magnet and helium bag.

Figure 2: The experimental setup. The sample is obscured by an electromagnet. The tube to the right of the magnet is a helium gas-jet cooler. At the top is the x-ray detector. A helium bag served to keep the sample ice-free during cooling.

Figure 3: A sketch of the experimental setup (not to scale) as photographed in Figure 2. The circularly polarized incident beam passes through a small hole in the magnet pole.

3. Results

Some of the main results of the experiment are shown below as a series of plots.

Figure 4: The (0016) Bragg-case standing wave, observed via its effect on the total fluorescence signal, just above the Ho L3 edge. Blue: Si (111) monochromator reflection. Orange: Si (333) monochromator reflection. While the standing wave is more pronounced with the lower-bandwidth Si (333) (as expected) there was an intensity loss of three orders of magnitude. This is likely to have arisen from the increased sensitivity to strain, exacerbated by the fact that four crystal reflections were required for the beam to exit the monochromator. The normal Si (111) reflection was used for all subsequent reflections as the intensity loss was too great for the proposed experiment. Eta is the primary crystal rotation angle, equivalent to the Bragg theta angle, to within an offset.

Figure 5: The (0016) Bragg reflection and fluorescence signal (standing wave), taken at an energy of 8.2 keV, above the L3 edge, where the two-theta value was low enough for the Bragg peak to be measured directly. Note the classic antisymmetric shape of the standing wave. Both signals are rescaled.

Figure 6: The fluorescence signal (standing wave) taken with linear and circular polarization. In general, the standing wave intensity is reduced with circular polarization because only one (sigma) polarization component is in the same direction for incident and scattered waves. Close to backscattering one would expect to see the same contrast for linear and circular polarization, which is clearly the case here.

Figure 7: The fluorescence standing wave intensity for various energies, centred on their calculated angles. The presence of other reflections can clearly be seen at various energies as 'spurious' glitches. Theta is the rotation angle about the normal to the scattering plane, shown relative to the measured Bragg reflection.

Figure 8: The field-strength dependence of XMCD at $T=20$ K, 8.075 keV, showing that the magnetization is saturated with the available field. (Not in standing-wave condition). Negative field values represent the field strength in the reversed direction.

Figure 9: The temperature-dependent XMCD at 8.075 keV. The signal shows a reversal at $T \sim 135$ K as the magnetic compensation point is crossed. The magnitude of the XMCD (Ho moment) increases continuously as temperature is reduced until about $T = 30$ K, where the increase in anisotropy pulls the moment towards the $\{111\}$ easy axes and away from the $\{001\}$ surface normal. Note: the XMCD signals in Figs 8 & 9 are not at the peak energy as the phase plate energy could not be adjusted at this point in the experiment. (Not in standing-wave condition). Outlying data points, caused by transient counting fluctuations, are common and have not been removed from the plot.

Figure 10: The XMCD (fractional fluorescence difference) energy spectrum and total fluorescence. Despite the low difference signal (measurements were restricted to $T = 300$ K following a failure of the cooler), the results of multiple scans, repeated with opposite primary polarization (positive and negative photon helicity), show very small statistical and systematic errors. (Not in standing-wave condition).

Figure 11: Detector integrated intensity vs photon energy in keV ('DCMenergy') near the Ho L3 edge (top) and calculated fraction of signal arising from the Ho L3 edge (bottom).

4. Conclusions and future work

Despite the fact that the phase plate energy was not able to be varied for the start of the experiment, and gas-jet cooler failed towards the end, the results were very valuable. We were able to conclude that the combination of weak XMCD and weak standing-wave contrast made observation of the wave-field-dependent XMCD impractical in this sample. We found a fortuitous coincidence of a high-quality ferromagnetic crystal with appropriate crystal structure and a Bragg reflection close to backscattering at the absorption edge of a magnetic ion (Ho L3) in HoIG. However, the presence of iron (Fe K-edge being a little lower in energy than Ho L3) limited both the XMCD (increased absorption and increased background) and standing-wave contrast (increased absorption). Our results suggest that a different sample would be required to convincingly observe the effect of superchiral XMCD, i.e. one with all the attributes outlined above but no 'parasitic' heavy ion. The search for a suitable material is underway.

In the meantime, observation of the compensation point has renewed our interest in the properties of magnetic domains where magnetic dipolar interactions can be turned off, and a study of this phenomenon will be the subject of a future proposal.

Finally, we note that our XMCD signals appear much smaller than those reported in the literature [3], which suggests a maximum effect of $\sim 1\%$. However, closer examination shows that the signals are, in fact, in very good agreement after taking into account differences in definitions and type of measurement. Considering peaks A and D in [3], corresponding to the first and third peaks in the dichroic spectrum from this work:

Peak A:

Shimomi *et al* [3]

$$\Delta\mu/\mu \sim 0.5\%$$

$$(\mu^+-\mu^-)/(\mu^++\mu^-) \sim 0.25\% \text{ (divide by 2: sum rather than mean)}$$

This work

$$\Delta I/I \sim 0.033\%$$

Fraction of signal from Ho L3 ~ 0.15 (see Fig. 11)

$$\Delta I/I \text{ (L3)} \sim 0.033/0.15 \sim 0.22\%$$

Peak B:

Shimomi *et al* [3]

$$\Delta\mu/\mu \sim 0.2\%$$

$$(\mu^+-\mu^-)/(\mu^++\mu^-) \sim 0.1\% \text{ (divide by 2: sum rather than mean)}$$

This work

$$\Delta I/I \sim 0.05\%$$

Fraction of signal from Ho L3 ~ 0.5 (see Fig. 11)

$$\Delta I/I \text{ (L3)} \sim 0.05/0.5 \sim 0.1\%$$

The corrected dichroic signals from this work and [3] are expected to be very similar except for a small reduction with the fluorescence technique (present work) due to self-absorption. The signals from Shimomi *et al* [3] and the present work do indeed agree remarkably well, despite initial apparent differences.

The plots in this report were generated by the Jupyter notebook HoIG_sept_2019.ipynb.

5. References

- [1] S. W. Lovesey, J. T. Collins & S. P. Collins *Phys. Rev. B* **99**, 054428 (2019)
- [2] A. Boothroyd (*Private communication*)
- [3] K. Shimomi *et al*, *Jpn.J.Appl.Phys.* **32** 314-316 *Suppl.* 32-2 (1993)

6. Publications resulting from this work

TBC